

SZ-BB-III-01-01 Networking of vocational school pupil from different vocational schools (English)

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Title	Networking of vocational school pupil from different vocational schools
Educational area	#vocational-training
Persona	P: Jasper - Trainee https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13951522
Short description	Vocational school student Jasper has to deal with the topic of “electrical engineering” for an upcoming exam and would like to network with another person.
Result	Networking and exchange on the topic of “Electrical Engineering”.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Part 1: "Search for work materials"• Part 2: "Networking"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Jasper is registered at BIRD• Jasper is logged in to BIRD• At least one other vocational school student is registered on BIRD and has a Buddy Finder profile.
Components	#learningpathfinder #chat #workspace #buddyfinder
Services / tools	#video-conference #eduki

Problem scenario

Introduction

Jasper Kempe is a first-year apprentice. He is training to be an industrial mechanic at Zeiss and is very interested in electrical engineering. He is currently preparing for an oral exam on this topic at his vocational school. He prefers speaking with a single person because they can respond to him and he doesn't have to follow several people at once in the conversation, who might all end up talking too quickly.

Problem definition

Jasper wants to learn more about electrical engineering and look for materials and resources he can use for studying and preparing for his exams. He also wants to exchange ideas with others or learn together. However, the study group that some of his classmates from vocational school have started isn't necessarily his first choice, as a larger group isn't right for him.

Background and context

Jasper always wants to be well prepared for the exams in his apprenticeship – whether oral or written. Learning for this is important to him, even if time management isn't always easy for him. He struggles to properly allocate his time before the exam date so he doesn't have to cram at the last minute. He knows that the various exams and tests are essential cornerstones of his apprenticeship, and good results are crucial for his progress and his chances of being hired. Furthermore, Jasper wants to acquire as much theoretical knowledge as possible that he can use later in his job.

Jasper's native language is French. An oral exam in which he has to answer questions in German is a challenge for him, even though he speaks the language quite well. He has only been in Germany for a year. Being adequately prepared for the exam situation is therefore important to him.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

To better prepare for his exams, Jasper would like to exchange with other vocational school students and someone with whom he can study or who can quiz him. Since he wants to not only memorize the exam material but also practice answering questions directly, he is looking for someone who has patience when he sometimes spends a little longer searching for the right words or a formulation.

Besides the opportunity to connect with other vocational school students, Jasper also values access to relevant learning materials. Jasper gets easily distracted while searching online and disappears into rabbit holes. He therefore often invests too much time in research and ends up with less time for the actual learning. Because of his ambition and high expectations of himself, this situation stresses him out, and he is looking for a solution.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Jasper spends most of his time learning alone at home with the materials he has from school. In the past, he has tried to join his classmates' study group at the vocational school. Because of the lack of interaction with his classmates, he worries about missing

important information or not being able to reach his full potential.

Jasper would like to use additional materials that are also recommended, but which are not so easy to find via search results on the internet. He first checks YouTube to see if he can find any tutorials. Although the research has yielded many results, Jasper still feels that he is not making good use of all the resources available to him.

Activity scenario

Part 1: "Search for work materials"

Step 1: Jasper opens the LearningPathFinder.

Step 2: The learning support chatbot opens and greets him. Jasper says he wants to study electrical engineering. Since Jasper has indicated to BIRD that he is training to be an industrial mechanic and is in his first year of apprenticeship, the system already knows his starting point and Jasper does not need to formulate it again. The AI chatbot guides Jasper to a suitable learning path based on his initial situation and his goals.

Step 3: Jasper specifies exactly when the exam is, what he wants to achieve, and when he believes he will be able to reach his goal. Here, he benefits from the fact that learning objectives are defined in the curriculum.

Step 4: Jasper displays a list of relevant learning resources, including a reference to teaching materials for vocational schools on eduki.

Step 5: Using the link provided by the chatbot, Jasper navigates to the eduki platform and logs in with his SSO access.

Step 6: Jasper selects the worksheet "Star-delta starting of three-phase motors" and begins to work on it. The system automatically saves the progress.

Step 7: After successfully finding learning materials, the learningPathFinder-Chatbot asks if Jasper would like to be connected with another person.

Part 2: "Networking"

Step 1: Since Jasper wanted to exchange with others about electrical engineering anyway, he agrees. Then the BuddyFinder will be suggested to him.

Step 2: Jasper is now switching from Learningpathfinder to BuddyFinder.

Step 3: Jasper is looking for a learning buddy. For the search, he checks whether his information in the BIRD profile is still up-to-date and suitable for his search, and also allows data sharing.

Step 4: Jasper also makes sure to provide information about his language level and the location where potential meetings could take place (online & in person). He submits his search request.

Step 5: BIRD notes in his to-dos for achieving the goal that the first step towards this goal has been taken.

Step 6: He now receives a notification in BIRD (and on his networked email address) that the BuddyFinder has found several possible buddies that match Jasper's (search)

criteria.

Step 7: Jasper decides to exchange with a single person who meets many of the criteria and is also a vocational school pupil.

Step 8: Jasper sees that the other vocational school pupil has accepted the contact request.

Step 9: Jasper and vocational school pupil XY communicate via chat and arrange a date to discuss the topic in person using the video conferencing tool and to learn together.